

TerraDT

D 17.1

Communication, dissemination and engagement strategy and plan

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D17.1 - Communication, dissemination and engagement strategy and plan

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DestinE	Destination Earth
DT	Digital Twin
DTC	Digital Twin Component
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EVE	Earth Virtualisation Engines
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
ML	Machine Learning
PR	Press Release
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
UAG	User Advisory Group
WP	Work Package

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Digital Twin, Dissemination, Communication, Stakeholder Engagement, Climate

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the overarching strategy for communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement across the 48-month duration of the TerraDT project. Moreover, the deliverable also provides a preliminary view on the exploitation pathways that will be explored by the project. The strategy presented here defines how the project will build visibility, foster interaction with key user communities, and support the uptake and sustainability of its results. It contributes directly to the **third core objective of the project: ensuring adoption of TerraDT outputs through a user-centric approach**.

The deliverable outlines the rationale, objectives, and structure of the project's outreach activities, implemented through Pillar 7 and distributed across three dedicated work packages (WP17–WP19). It introduces a campaign-based approach for communication, supported by targeted dissemination actions and structured stakeholder engagement mechanisms, including those tailored to the project's four core impact modelling domains: sea ice, land ice, forest, and urban.

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been defined to track outputs and engagement across digital channels, events, publications, and cross-sector interactions. The strategy is supported by shared tools, regular coordination mechanisms, and alignment with project milestones and stakeholder needs.

This document serves as a practical reference for the implementation of external-facing activities and will guide project communication, stakeholder involvement, and visibility throughout the entire lifecycle of TerraDT.

This deliverable is also intended as a **living document**. It may be updated in part or in full over the course of the project to reflect evolving priorities, lessons learned, or new opportunities. Any substantial revision will be undertaken in agreement with the Project Management Office and, where appropriate, in coordination with the European Commission, to ensure that the strategy continues to serve the best interests of the project, including in response to information and developments that may not yet be known at this stage.

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1. Introduction

The TerraDT project – *Digital Twin of Earth system for Cryosphere, Land surface and related interactions* – contributes to the European Commission’s Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative by developing a modular, scalable and interoperable Digital Twin for critical Earth system components. Kicked-off in January 2025 and running until December 2028, the project aims to improve climate projections and impact assessments for decision-making by advancing modelling capabilities related to the cryosphere, land surface, and their interactions, and by enabling their integration into the broader DestinE infrastructure, building on previous efforts in high-resolution Earth system modelling.

More precisely, the project pursues three main objectives:

1. **Build and deploy a digital twin of the Earth system** for Cryosphere, Land surface and related interactions to provide improved climate projections and impact assessments for decision-making.
2. **Develop a modular, scalable and interoperable TerraDT infrastructure** to further enhance the DestinE infrastructure for software, high-performance computing and data handling.
3. **Ensure uptake of the TerraDT results by scientific community and users from public and private sectors** through engagement activities and by implementing a user-centric approach.

Recognising the central role of stakeholder interaction in meeting these objectives, and especially the third one, TerraDT has established **Pillar 7 – Communication, Engagement and Sustainability**, which spans the full duration of the project through three dedicated Work Packages: **WP17 (M1–M18)**, **WP18 (M19–M36)**, and **WP19 (M37–M48)**. These activities combine targeted outreach, visibility, and co-creation of value with external stakeholders, alongside long-term strategies for adoption and sustainability of project outputs. The pillar also supports strategic alignment with other European and international digital twin initiatives, notably through synergies with DestinE and Horizon Europe-funded sister projects.

The present deliverable, submitted at month 5 of the project lifetime, provides the overarching strategy for the Pillar 7 activities and details the implementation plan. This deliverable is to be intended as a living document which will be updated as the project evolves to ensure flexibility and support impact maximisation. For instance, it may be updated in part or in full over the course of the project to reflect evolving priorities, lessons learned, or new opportunities. Any substantial revision will be undertaken in agreement with the Project Management Office and, where appropriate, in coordination with the European Commission, to ensure that the strategy continues to serve the best interests of the project.

A formal update to this deliverable will be presented in D19.2 – Communication, dissemination and engagement - final report, due at the end of the project.

The document is structured as follows:

- ❖ **Section 2** presents the stakeholder engagement objectives, stakeholder engagement plan, the engagement pathways for the impact models (sea ice, land ice, forest and urban), and the alignment with DestinE and other relevant initiatives.
- ❖ **Section 3** outlines the communication and dissemination strategy, including objectives, phased implementation, thematic campaigns, communication channels, visual identity, and planned actions related to the website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and events.
- ❖ **Section 4** details the key performance indicators (KPIs), working modalities, and shared tools supporting implementation, coordination, and monitoring of the presented plan.

- ❖ **Section 5** introduces the structure and early directions of the exploitation strategy, to be then updated in D18.1 – Exploitation and sustainability plan, to be submitted in M20.
- ❖ **Section 6** concludes with key messages of the deliverable and the next steps.

2. Stakeholder engagement strategy and plan

2.1 Stakeholder engagement objectives

The stakeholder engagement activities correspond to the third main objective outlined in section 1. Engagement is essential to guarantee that the project outputs, beyond being scientifically robust, are also fit for purpose, user-accessible, and aligned with the operational needs of decision-makers, practitioners, and technical communities. This overarching goal translates into five specific stakeholder engagement objectives:

- ❖ **Objective E1: Involve users** from public and private sectors in the co-development of impact models to create fit for purpose solutions.
- ❖ **Objective E2: Ensure user uptake** of the TerraDT solutions.
- ❖ **Objective E3: Mobilise relevant stakeholders** other than users, including **policy makers, funders and public authorities** to ensure relevance and sustainability of the solutions developed by the project
- ❖ **Objective E4: Ensure the strategic and technical alignment with DestinE** and other relevant initiatives and projects to anchor the TerraDT developments to the European and global digital twin landscape.
- ❖ **Objective E5: Promote best practices and relevant standards** adopted by the project at global level.

2.2 Stakeholder analysis and targeted engagement plans

The primary stakeholders of the TerraDT project are the users of the four impact models. In addition, other key stakeholders - such as policy makers, funders, DestinE, research institutions and related projects – will play a critical role. Engaging with these groups is essential to support the co-development of the TerraDT solutions and to ensure their effective positioning and adoption within the international landscape.

2.2.1 Sea ice impact model

The sea ice impact model is designed to provide both operational and strategic insights for decision-makers and developers in cold-region marine environments, primarily the Baltic and Arctic sea (Svalbard region), although applicable to any other geographical area with similar challenges.

The sea ice impact model supports:

- ❖ **Climatological analysis:** Mapping historical and projected ice presence, severity, and the duration of various ice conditions (e.g., mild, moderate, severe). This helps establish baselines for design and planning.
- ❖ **Extreme value analysis:** Estimating return levels for ice-related variables (e.g., maximum thickness or pressure events), producing **return value maps** that are critical for structural design, permitting, and safety assessments.
- ❖ **Lagrangian drift simulations:** Modeling how ice deforms and moves around offshore structures. This helps in understanding ice load risks, planning icebreaker routes, and minimising coastal impact.

Primary users of the model, include:

- ❖ **Offshore infrastructure developers:** They can use model outputs to assess ice load risks and design safe installations (e.g., jetties, platforms).
- ❖ **Wind park operators and planners:** They can assess how wind farm structures interact with sea ice, including potential deformed drift patterns.
- ❖ **Harbor operators and shipowners:** They can anticipate ice conditions that could affect navigation, shipping lanes, and port operations.
- ❖ **Icebreakers and maritime traffic planners:** They can optimise routes and operations based on predicted drift and severity.
- ❖ **Local communities and municipalities:** They can understand potential impacts of offshore development on coastal ice conditions and safety.

The following table includes some examples of potential users that will be engaged by the project:

Potential TerraDT sea ice impact model users	Engagement Purpose
Utilitas (Gulf of Riga) and Vattenfall (Baltic Sea), ConX (FSRU jetty at Paldiski)	sea infrastructure development
Estonian Transport Administrations, Ice services in Finland (FMI), Estonia (ESTE) and Sweden (SMHI), Traficom, Finnish transport infrastructure agency	navigation, design for new icebreaker
Tallinna Sadam (Port of Tallinn) and other ports in Finland and Estonia	future port operation design

Table 1 - Sea ice impact model targeted engagement purpose

In addition to the primary users, there are other relevant stakeholders that need to be considered for the sea ice impact model:

- ❖ **DestinE:** To understand the potential integration of the impact model in DestinE and align expectations with the DestinE entrusted entities.
- ❖ **Policy makers and regulators** (such as Environmental Agencies, national weather services, etc.): Can use model outputs to inform maritime regulations, coastal zone management, and climate adaptation policies.
- ❖ **Funding agencies:** Can support data integration, model expansion, and long-term maintenance.
- ❖ **International organisations** (such as the International Maritime Organisation - IMO, the Arctic organisations - Arctic Council, Arctic Circle, Arctic Portal, FAO, ICES): Might adopt and further promote the usage of the impact model.
- ❖ **Research institutes and technical developers:** Provide scientific support, model validation, and development of advanced features.
- ❖ **Public and environmental advocacy groups:** Interested in understanding how offshore structures affect coastal ecosystems and community resilience.
- ❖ **Other relevant projects/initiatives:** Including, among others, NOCOS DT, Digital Twin Ocean, EDITO, EMODnet.

The following table summarises the main engagement activities foreseen for the sea ice impact model:

Timeline	Engagement actions	Targeted stakeholders
M5-M24	Identification of key stakeholders for the identified target groups	All stakeholders
M13-M38	2 online impact sector workshops for the Arctic region to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where users compare model predictions to historical or operational data (in collaboration with the land ice impact model)	Users
M13 - M30	2 online impact sector workshops for the Baltic region to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where users compare model predictions to historical or operational data	Users
M15-M43	5 Multi-stakeholder roundtables (every six months), jointly organised with the TerraDT sister projects (UrbanAir and WeatherGenerator - see sub section 2.2.7), with representatives from DestinE (ESA , EUMETSAT , ECMWF) to align expectations and explore synergies	DestinE, sister projects
M30-M42	2 online user training sessions organised in collaboration with Pillar 5	Users
M5-M48	Continuous engagement of the scientific community via participation to scientific conferences and through scientific publications	Research institutes and technical developers
M25	1 Online workshop with policy makers / regulators from the Arctic and Baltic area for early integration into guidance and	Policy makers, funders

	frameworks and resulting policy briefings (in collaboration with the land ice impact model)	
M39	1 in-person policy impact event to present the work done with regulators and the resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders
M48	In-person final event to present the achievements of the sea ice impact model	All stakeholders
M1-M48	Participation to relevant third party events	All stakeholders

Table 2 - Sea ice impact model targeted engagement plan

2.2.2. Land ice impact model

The land ice impact model is designed to address the effects of retreating Arctic glaciers on sea level rise and related topics. The model will provide new opportunities to study the interactions between ice sheets and the oceans on a global scale with unprecedented detail. This will ultimately lead to a more reliable quantification of future sea-level rise, in particular on the decadal time-scale. The developments will be piloted in Svalbard with further potential adoption in Greenland and Antarctica.

The primary user of the model is the **tourism industry in Svalbard**: Use the model to understand the impact of retreating glaciers on tourism and transportation.

In addition to the primary users, there are other relevant stakeholders that need to be considered for the land ice impact model:

- ❖ **The global research community working on sea level rise**: Understand potential impacts of retreating glaciers on ecological ecosystems, provide scientific support, model validation, and development of advanced features.
- ❖ **Land transportation and tourism industry in the Greenland and Antarctic region**: Use the model to understand the impact of retreating glaciers on tourism and transportation.
- ❖ **Policy makers and regulators** (such as the Norwegian government, e.g. Ministry of environment): Can use model outputs to inform maritime regulations, coastal zone management, and tourism related policies.
- ❖ **Local newspapers**: Svalbard post (newspaper), and Aftenposten (main paper of Norway), and NRK, the main Norwegian news channel.
- ❖ **DestinE**: To understand the potential integration of the impact model in DestinE and align expectations with the DestinE entrusted entities

The following table summarises the main engagement activities foreseen for the land ice impact model:

Timeline	Engagement actions	Targeted stakeholders
M5-M24	Identification of key stakeholders for the identified	All stakeholders

	target groups and community building	
M13-M38	2 impact sector workshops for the Arctic region to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where users compare model predictions to historical or operational data (in collaboration with the sea ice impact model)	Users
M15-M43	5 online Multi-stakeholder roundtables (every six months), jointly organised with the sister projects, with representatives from DestinE (ESA , EUMETSAT , ECMWF) to align expectations and explore synergies	DestinE, Sister projects
M30-M42	2 online user training sessions organised in collaboration with Pillar 5	Users
M5-M48	Continuous engagement of the scientific community via participation to scientific conferences and through scientific publications	Research institutes and technical developers
M25	1 Online workshop with policy makers / regulators from the Arctic area for early integration into guidance and frameworks and resulting policy briefings (in collaboration with the sea ice impact model)	Policy makers, funders
M39	1 in person policy impact event to present the work done with regulators and the resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders
M48	In person final event to present the achievements of the land ice impact model	All stakeholders
M1-M48	Participation to relevant third party events	All stakeholders

Table 3 - Land ice impact model targeted engagement plan

2.2.3. Forest impact model

The forest impact model informs forestry, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity actions.

Primary users of the model, include:

- ❖ **Forest service companies:** Forest service companies offer specific services in the forest sector. These companies may be, for example, technical operators or forest consulting companies. The specific services include, for instance, forest management services, harvesting services, carbon balancing, and digital solutions. They can use the TerraDT output as follows:
 - ◆ Tool for monitoring and predicting forest disturbances (storm, fire, insects)
 - ◆ Tool for converting carbon flows into financial products
 - ◆ Source of information for consultancies
- ❖ **Forest and wood industry:** Industry concerned with forestry, logging, timber trade, and the production of wood-based and other forest products. They can use the impact model to:
 - ◆ Ensure sustainable wood supply
 - ◆ Monitor climate change mitigation targets
 - ◆ Compute the end-to-end carbon cycle of forests and products
 - ◆ Plan long term strategies (estimating future raw material sources for defining mill locations)
- ❖ **Forestry enterprises:** State forest enterprises are responsible for the management of almost half of European forests (44%), while the other half is managed by private owners (56%). About 76% of private forest areas are owned by individuals or families and to a lesser amount by business entities. They can use the TerraDT model for:
 - ◆ long-term forest management decisions
 - ◆ monitoring and predicting forest disturbances (storm, fire, insects)
- ❖ **Governmental and non-governmental bodies & International organisations:** Governmental forestry bodies contain ministries, state forestry commissions, and administrations at both national and county levels. They form the formal institutional framework for forest regulations, policies, legislations, technical norms, and operational guidelines. They can use the impact model to:
 - ◆ simulate climate change scenarios for specific forest areas
 - ◆ provide verified and reliable facts and data for policymakers and public parties to support discussion and debate on forest policies
 - ◆ provide information for forest owners on possible risks (storm, fire, insects)
- ❖ **Scientific users and forest research organisations:** Any private or legal entities involved in forest science. This involves universities, scientists, students, etc., and international, national, regional, county or provincial level research organisations dealing with forest monitoring, policy advice, training, and knowledge transfer. Most of them have a legal mandate for their research and advising role. They can use the impact model to:
 - ◆ merge climate forcing factors
 - ◆ provide standardized information across countries and regions

The following table includes some examples of potential users that will be engaged by the project:

Potential impact model users	TerraDT forest	Examples of stakeholders
Forest service companies		CLC, Repsol Foundation, Tornator Oyj (Finland), Unique Land Use (Germany)
Forest and wood industry		Tornator Oyj (Finland), Stora Enso (Finland), IKEA (Sweden)
Forestry enterprises		Tornator Oyj (Finland), Forstwirtschaftliche Vereinigung Schwarzwald eG (Germany), ForstBW (Germany), Stora Enso (Finland), Forest District Renasterea Padurii (Romania), Forest District Sfanta Maria (Romania)
Governmental and non-governmental bodies & International organisations		FAO, EEA, DG (Clima / Env), JRC, Forest Europe, Ministry of Environment, Water and Forest of Romania (Romania), FAO (International), GIZ Madagascar (International), European Environment Agency (EEA) (International), UNECE-FAO, Forestry and timber section (International), State Forest Administration Baden Württemberg (LFW) (Germany), Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland (Finland), IBL Forest Research Institute (Poland), Metsähallitus (Finland)

Table 4 - Forest impact model targeted stakeholders

In addition to the primary users, there are other relevant stakeholders that need to be considered for the forest impact model:

- ❖ **DestinE:** To understand the potential integration of the impact model in DestinE and align expectations with the DestinE entrusted entities
- ❖ Research institutes and technical developers with special focus on the climate community
- ❖ Other relevant projects/initiatives: ESA Forest Twin Project¹

The following table summarises the main engagement activities foreseen for the forest impact model:

Timeline	Engagement actions	Targeted stakeholders
M5-M24	Identification of key stakeholders for the identified target groups	Users
M13- M24	Contribution to the user workshop will be organised by the ESA Forest Twin Project	Users
M24-M38	1 online impact sector workshops to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where	Users

¹ <https://www.foresttwin.org/>

	users compare model predictions to historical or operational data.	
M15-M43	5 online multi-stakeholder roundtables (every six months), jointly organised with the sister projects, with representatives from DestinE (ESA , EUMETSAT , ECMWF) to align expectations and explore synergies	DestinE, sister projects
M30-M42	2 online user training sessions organised in collaboration with Pillar 6	Users
M5-M48	Continuous engagement of the scientific community via participation to scientific conferences and through scientific publications	Research institutes and technical developers
M32	1 online workshop with policy makers / regulators from the forestry area for early integration into guidance and frameworks and resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders
M39	1 in person policy impact event to present the work done with regulators and the resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders
M48	In person final event to present the achievements of the forest impact model	All stakeholders
M1-M48	Participation to relevant third party events	All stakeholders

Table 5 - Forest impact model targeted engagement plan

2.2.4. Urban impact model

The **urban impact model** aims to address urban climate issues, including carbon sequestration and climate extremes. The carbon sequestration and climate extreme sub-modules will work together to measure urban carbon capture, identify areas vulnerable to temperature extremes, and evaluate nature-based solutions for their effects on carbon sequestration and urban temperature regulation under current and future climate scenarios. (The temporal scale included into the model will be the main added value brought by the project to provide reliable forecasts.)

Primary users of the model, include:

- ❖ **City/urban planners from public sector local authorities** starting with the six metropolitan areas in focus for the project (Lisbon, Barcelona, Munich, Paris, Helsinki and Zurich) and reaching out to other cities in Europe
- ❖ National weather and health services and environmental agencies to be aware of planning strategies and potential risks
- ❖ Real estate investors and insurance companies for planning purposes.

The following table includes some examples of potential users that will be engaged by the project:

Potential impact model users	TerraDT urban	Examples of stakeholders
Local authorities and municipalities		City/ Urban planners from the six target metropolitan areas (Lisbon, Barcelona, Munich, Paris, Helsinki and Zurich) and from EU at large
National weather and health services and environmental agencies		FMI, IPMA, DWD etc., UBA (German environmental agency), APA (Portuguese env. agency) etc., national NHS <i>Initial focus on the 6 metropolitan areas addressed by the project and then on other EU countries</i>
Real estate investors and insurance companies		Real estate investors and insurance companies in the six metropolitan areas addressed by the project

Table 6 - Urban impact model targeted stakeholders

In addition to the primary users, there are other relevant stakeholders that need to be considered for the urban impact model:

- ❖ EU environmental agency and DestinE (primarily ESA and ECMWF): To understand the potential integration of the impact model in DestinE and align expectations with the DestinE entrusted entities and create awareness about the model with the EU environmental agency.
- ❖ International organisations such as the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), the Global Heat Resilience Service, the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO): the main purpose of the engagement is to raise awareness about the usage of the impact model.
- ❖ Research institutions and scientists (Universities and research centres conducting studies on urban climate and environmental impacts): Provide scientific support, model validation, and development of advanced features.
- ❖ Other potential users: Once the model and the user interface are ready, they will be promoted to an extended set of potential users including citizen organisations, energy companies, biodiversity and health organisations.
- ❖ Other relevant projects/initiatives: sister project URBANair.

The following table summarises the main engagement activities foreseen for the urban impact model:

Timeline	Engagement actions	Targeted stakeholders
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M5-M18	Identification of key stakeholders for the identified target groups from the 6 target metropolitan areas	Users
M19-M40	Creation of a user community beyond the six metropolitan areas targeted by the project	Users
M13-M38	2 impact sector workshops in two of the cities targeted by the project to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where users compare model predictions to historical or operational data 2 online workshops targeting private sector (e.g. real estates and insurance companies)	Users
M15-M48	Multi-stakeholder roundtables (every six months), jointly organised with the sister projects, with representatives from DestinE (ESA , EUMETSAT , ECMWF) to align expectations and explore synergies	DestinE, sister projects
M30-M42	2 online user training organised in collaboration with Pillar 6	City/ Urban planners
M5-M48	Continuous engagement of the scientific community via participation to scientific conferences and through scientific publications	Research institutes and technical developers
M27	1 online workshop with policy makers / regulators from national/EU weather services for early integration into guidance and frameworks and resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders
M39	1 in person policy impact event to present the work done with regulators and the resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders

M48	In person final event to present the achievements of the sea ice impact model	All stakeholders
M18-M48	Local outreach activities in the six metropolitan areas performed by the TerraDT partners	Users
M40-M48	Promotional campaigns to secondary target users (i.e. citizen organisations, energy companies, biodiversity and health organisations)	Other users
M1-M48	Participation to relevant third party events	All stakeholders

Table 7 - Urban impact model targeted engagement plan

2.2.5. The TerraDT User Advisory Group (UAG)

The purpose of the TerraDT User Advisory Group (UAG) is to provide support from the perspective of the users coming from impact sectors and research institutions. The group will work closely with pillar 7 under the co-creation and user engagement tasks and will be consulted at critical milestones. The UAG will provide input during the development process and feedback on the potential uptake of the outputs upon delivery of adoptable results. The TerraDT UAG members are:

- ❖ Jaana Bäck (Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures - ENVRI),
- ❖ Werner Kutsch (Director general, Integrated Carbon Observatory System - ICOS ERIC).
- ❖ Markku Markkula (Vice-President European Committee of the Regions President Helsinki-Uusimaa Region),
- ❖ Anu Riikonen (Senior landscape planning specialist, Sitowise),
- ❖ Paulo Nogueira (Director, Biostatistics Autonomous Disciplinary Area (Laboratory of Biomathematics, University of Lisbon, Portugal).

A first webinar will be organised in spring 2025 to introduce the objectives of the project to the UAG. Four extra online meetings (M18, M24, M34, M44) are planned with the UAG to collect their feedback and input on the impact models. The UAG will be also invited to the other main project events.

2.2.6. Destination Earth

The European Commission's flagship initiative Destination Earth (DestinE) develops a digital twin of the whole Earth, jointly implemented by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), the European Space Agency (ESA), and the European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). The DestinE system's main components are the Service Platform (DESP) that serves as the primary interface to end-users, the Data Lake (DEDL) where data is stored, and the Digital Twin Engine (DTE) that is used to run the different digital twins. DestinE's first priority DTs are the Climate Change Adaptation DT (Climate DT) and Weather-Induced Extremes DT (Extremes DT). DestinE uses the twins to model, monitor and simulate natural phenomena, hazards and the related human activities in order to provide accurate information on environmental changes and support decision making.

In addition to enhancing the DestinE infrastructure by integrating new modular digital twin components, TerraDT contributes to the advancement of science and demonstrates practical use of DestinE data. TerraDT's **Strategic Advisory Board (SAB)** is planned to be leveraged to ensure the strategic alignment with DestinE and other key initiatives at high level. In addition to that the project will organise six **multi-stakeholder roundtables** (every six months) engaging the projects funded under the same call, to establish a regular dialogue with the DestinE entrusted entities (ESA, EUMETSAT , ECMWF).

2.2.7. Other relevant DT projects

In addition to the DestinE twins, there are other ongoing DT projects that have natural connection potential to TerraDT.

Nordic Cryosphere DT (NOCOS DT)	
Why is it relevant	NOCOS DT develops sea ice related models and applications that have special synergy with the Sea ice impact model.
Potential engagement actions	Sharing models, workflows, or data related to Destination Earth.
Duration	2.2023–12.2023 (phase 1), 1.2024–10.2025 (phase 2)
Main contact point	CSC
Destination Earth Climate Change Adaptation DT (Climate DT)	
Why is it relevant	Climate DT is one of Destination Earth priority DTs, and TerraDT is being developed with a strong focus on integration with DestinE, particularly with the Climate DT. Furthermore, the impact models developed within TerraDT are intended to be onboarded onto the DestinE Service Platform. Both projects share the same core climate models, ensuring consistency and alignment.
Potential engagement actions	Leveraging the advancements and best practices from Climate DT. Align workflows and data governance with DestinE standards to ensure compatibility and seamless integration.
Duration	9.2022–4.2024 (phase 1), 5.2024–4.2026 (phase 2)
Main contact point	CSC
Destination Earth Weather-Induced Extremes DT (Extremes DT)	
Why is it relevant	Extremes DT is another high-priority DT of DestinE.
Potential engagement actions	Leveraging the developments and best practices from Extremes DT. Cross-DT collaboration.
Duration	9.2022–4.2024 (phase 1), 5.2024–4.2026 (phase 2)
Main contact point	CSC
UrbanAIR	
Why is it relevant	This project develops solutions for urban climate challenges.

Potential engagement actions	Cross-DT collaboration, using the experiences gained in the BioDT/DT-Geo/interTwin collaboration.
Duration	1.2025–12.2028
Main contact point	BSC
WeatherGenerator	
Why is it relevant	This project builds a European AI model for weather and climate and develops improved predictions.
Potential engagement actions	Cross-DT collaboration, using the experiences gained in the BioDT/DT-Geo/interTwin collaboration.
Duration	1.2025–12.2028
Main contact points	ETH, MPI-M
ESA Forest Digital Twin	
Why is it relevant	Forest DTC will create a pre-operational, end-to-end digital replica of real-world forest systems with initial focus on Europe.
Potential engagement actions	Cross-DT collaboration with the TerraDT forest impact model.
Duration	1.2025–12.2026
Main contact points	VTT

Table 8 - Other relevant DT projects

2.2.8. Other relevant data initiatives

TerraDT will also interact with the most relevant data-initiatives that are significant for the TerraDT developments, namely the Green Deal Data Space and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). TerraDT will follow the developments of these initiatives and will identify potential synergies and opportunities for collaborations to understand how to position its outputs in these major European endeavours.

2.2.9. Global actors and initiatives

TerraDT will contribute to consolidating the international network around the Destination Earth initiative, to establish the DestinE approach, data standards and best practices as the new norm for high-resolution Earth system modelling. This will be done partly through the international engagement activities of each impact model and partly through establishing contacts with relevant international actors listed below and in more detail in **Annex 1**.

In addition to the previously mentioned international initiatives, the following ones will be targeted:

Research Data Alliance (RDA)	
Why is it relevant	TerraDT/DestinE standards and practices should be aligned with RDA’s international recommendations and standards for research data management and interoperability.
Potential engagement actions	Contributions to RDA’s standardisation work

Timeline	Discussions to be initiated by 9.2025
Main contact point	CSC
Earth Virtualisation Engines (EVE) initiative	
Why is it relevant	TerraDT/DestinE standards and practices should inform the aim of the EVE initiative to improve the quality and accessibility of Earth system data and to create a digital commons to efficiently expose data to new methods of analysis and proactive information production.
Potential engagement actions	Contributions to the EVE initiative's work
Timeline	Discussions to be initiated by 9.2025
Main contact point	CSC
Digital Twin Consortium	
Why is it relevant	TerraDT focus areas could be included to the wide range of digital twins covered by the work of the Digital Twin Consortium that aims to foster development, raise awareness, increase adoption, and improve the interoperability of digital engineering projects propelled by digital twins.
Potential engagement actions	Contributions to the Digital Twin Consortium's awareness-raising and interoperability work
Timeline	Discussions to be initiated by 9.2025
Main contact point	TalTech
International standardisation organisations	
Why is it relevant	To make TerraDT's practices visible and technically aligned with global standards, engagement with international standardisation organisation organisations is needed, potentially through EU-funded mechanisms such as StandICT.eu and HSbooster.eu
Potential engagement actions	Contributions to international standardisation work
Timeline	Exploring opportunities by 6.2025
Main contact points	CSC, Trust-IT
Regional actors	
Why is it relevant	In addition to the high-level processes described above, TerraDT/DestinE standards and practices can be spread internationally at grassroots level through collaboration with partners developing digital twin solutions in regions outside Europe.
Potential engagement actions	Co-development of standards and best practices, joint contributions to the work of RDA, EVE and other international organisations
Timeline	Identification of most relevant partners by 9.2025 and establishing contacts with them by 12.2025
Main contact point	CSC

Table 9 - Global actors and initiatives

2.3. Stakeholder engagement timeline

The following table summarises the engagement plan for the TerraDT project.

Date	Engagement activity	Target stakeholders	Responsible
M1-M48	Participation to relevant third party events	All stakeholders	All TerraDT partners
M5	Establishment of the TerraDT User Advisory Group	UAG	Pillar 7
M5-M40	Identification of key stakeholders for the identified target groups	All stakeholders	All TerraDT partners - coordinated by Pillar 7
M5-M48	Continuous engagement of the scientific community via participation to scientific conferences and through scientific publications	Research institutes and technical developers	All TerraDT partners
M13-M38	<p>- 5 online impact sector workshops to collect user needs and to conduct validation activities where users compare model predictions to historical or operational data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2 for the sea/land ice impact model in the Arctic region ● 2 for the sea ice impact model Baltic region ● 1 online for the forest impact model <p>- 2 impact workshops for the urban model in two of the cities targeted by the project</p> <p>- 2 online workshops targeting private sector stakeholders for the urban model (e.g. real</p>	Impact model users	Pillar 7 + Pillar 5 + Pillar 6

	<p>estates and insurance companies)</p> <p>- Contribution to the user workshop that will be organised by the ESA Forest Twin Project</p>		
M15, M22, M29, M36, M43	<p>5 online multi-stakeholder roundtables (every six months), jointly organised with the TerraDT sister projects (UrbanAir and WeatherGenerator - see sub section 2.2.7), with representatives from DestinE (ESA, EUMETSAT , ECMWF) to align expectations and explore synergies</p>	DestinE, sister projects	All TerraDT partners - coordinated by Pillar 7
M18-M48	<p>Local outreach activities in the six metropolitan areas performed by the TerraDT partners</p>	Urban impact model users	Pillar 5 + Pillar 7
M18, M24, M34, M44	<p>4 online meetings with the UAG to collect their feedback and input on the impact models.</p>	UAG	Pillar 7
M25, M27, M32	<p>3 Online workshop with policy makers / regulators for early integration into guidance and frameworks and resulting policy briefings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 for the Arctic and Baltic area (impact models sea ice /land ice) M25 ● 1 for national/EU weather services (impact 	Policy makers, funders	Pillar 7 + Pillar 5 + Pillar 6

	model urban) M27 1 for policy makers / regulators from the forestry area (impact model forest) M32		
M30-M42	2 online user training for the 4 impact models organised in collaboration with Pillar 5/6	Users	Pillar 7 + Pillar 5 + Pillar 6
M39	1 in person policy impact event to present the work done with regulators and the resulting policy briefings	Policy makers, funders	All TerraDT partners - coordinated by Pillar 7
M40-M48	Promotional campaigns to secondary target users (i.e. citizen organisations, energy companies, biodiversity and health organisations)	Users urban impact model	Pillar 7 + Pillar 5
M48	In person final event to present the achievements of the sea ice impact model	All stakeholders	All TerraDT partners - coordinated by Pillar 7

Table 10 - Stakeholder engagement plan timeline

3. Communication and dissemination strategy and plan

3.1. Communication and dissemination objectives

Complementing the stakeholder engagement strategy outlined in the previous section, the communication and dissemination plan of TerraDT focuses on **targeted outreach** and **knowledge sharing** to support the visibility, credibility, and uptake of the project’s outputs. While engagement activities ensure direct interaction with key user communities to co-design and validate the Digital Twin Components (DTCs) and impact models, communication and dissemination actions serve to amplify these interactions, inform broader audiences, and position TerraDT within the European and global digital twin landscape. In particular, the strategy contributes to reinforcing TerraDT’s scientific and policy relevance, its integration into the DestinE framework, and the long-term usability of its results across stakeholder groups.

In line with Horizon Europe definitions, in the context of the present deliverable, **communication** refers to the strategic and coherent **promotion of the project** and its vision to multiple audiences—including the general public and media—through accessible and engaging formats. By contrast,

dissemination refers to the process of making the specific **results and knowledge generated by the project** available to specific target audiences—particularly researchers, policymakers, industry actors and impact model adopters—who can benefit from or build on them.

Communication and dissemination efforts are also designed to reinforce stakeholder engagement in relation to the project's core modelling areas. Each impact model—Sea Ice, Land Ice, Forest, and Urban—has a set of target users and engagement activities defined in section 2. The communication strategy complements these pathways by promoting progress in model development, early use cases, user profiles, and demonstrators through targeted content and thematic campaigns.

Leveraging on the third main project objective presented in section 1, the project aims to achieve the following more specific communication objectives:

- ❖ C1: Ensure high visibility of TerraDT's mission, objectives, and role in supporting the DestinE initiative, using accessible language and consistent branding across digital and physical communication materials.
- ❖ C2: Raise awareness of the societal relevance of TerraDT's contribution to climate change adaptation and mitigation, targeting media, general public, and non-specialist stakeholders.
- ❖ C3: Promote the project's activities and achievements through participation in strategic events, social media presence, newsletters, and engagement with European Commission channels.

The dissemination objectives instead include:

- ❖ **D1:** Facilitate broad access to TerraDT's **scientific and technical outputs**—including models, datasets, user stories, and demonstrators—by sharing them with **scientific communities, peer projects, and relevant EU and international initiatives**.
- ❖ **D2:** Support **interoperability and uptake of results** by providing timely information to targeted user communities, with a focus on transparency, standardisation alignment, and reuse potential.
- ❖ **D3:** Contribute to **policy and research agendas** by translating project findings into **actionable insights** for institutional actors and decision-makers in climate and digital policy domains.

3.2. Communication and dissemination strategy

TerraDT's communication and dissemination strategy is organised in **three successive and interlinked phases**, in line with the structure of the project's dedicated Work Package entitled "Communication, Engagement and Sustainability", which is implemented in three parts: WP17 (Part 1), WP18 (Part 2) and WP19 (Part 3). While the Work Package name remains consistent, each part corresponds to a different phase in the project lifecycle, reflecting an evolving focus in terms of communication and dissemination goals and intensity, as well as content maturity. These phases are structured to ensure alignment with the communication and dissemination objectives outlined in section 3.1 and to support the broader engagement strategy presented in the previous section.

3.2.1. Phase 1 - Establish (WP17, M01-18)

This first phase is dedicated to **establishing TerraDT's public presence and core messages**. Communication efforts will focus on increasing visibility (Objective C1) and articulating the project's role within the European Digital Twin ecosystem, in particular DestinE. Key activities include the creation and consistent adoption of the visual identity, the launch and continuous management and update of the website and social media channels, and the production of introductory materials. This

phase also includes the organisation of the first Impact Model Workshop (WS1) and the definition of key user profiles and journeys to support the design of the storytelling platform. Dissemination in this phase supports early awareness of the project objectives and early results (Objective D1) and facilitates links with relevant research communities and policy stakeholders. This phase will also introduce the project to target audiences at key events, laying the groundwork for future uptake (Objective D2).

3.2.2. Phase 2 - Expand (WP18, M19-36)

In the second phase, communication and dissemination efforts will be intensified to reflect the increasing **availability of intermediate results and validated components**. Communication will be intensified through more frequent updates, participation in third party conferences and the use of multimedia storytelling (Objectives C1, C2). Dissemination activities will focus on scientific outputs, use case demonstrations and contributions to standardisation and policy dialogues (objectives D2, D3). The second Impact Modelling Workshop (WS2) and the ongoing refinement of user pathways further strengthen the dissemination of early project outcomes. Particular emphasis will be placed on structured interactions with the **User Advisory Group** and relevant external initiatives to facilitate knowledge transfer and uptake (Objective D2), while strengthening TerraDT's contribution to European leadership in climate DT innovation (Objective C3). The communication surrounding the launch of the prototype storytelling platform becomes a central activity, enhancing visibility and supporting user engagement in anticipation of the final phase. In this phase, particular attention will ultimately be given to reinforcing the communication dimension of stakeholder engagement for each impact model. Stories and factsheets emerging from the Sea Ice, Land Ice, Forest, and Urban pathways will be promoted through both thematic campaigns and social media spotlights. This will help expand the visibility of domain-specific engagement actions and build continuity between user interaction and result dissemination.

3.2.3. Phase 3 - Consolidate (WP19, M37-48)

In the final phase, communication and dissemination activities will converge to ensure the **sustainable impact and accessibility of the project results**. Communication aims to summarise the project's legacy and promote its achievements through a Policy Impact workshop, and the organisation of a final event and outreach, also via EU and international channels (Objectives C1, C3). Dissemination will focus on long-term usability and policy relevance, including open access to models, datasets and guidelines, whenever possible (Objectives D1, D3). This phase will culminate in the finalisation of the TerraDT digital storytelling platform and adoption toolkit, consolidating knowledge transfer (Objective D2) and ensuring that the results of the project remain accessible and actionable beyond the project duration.

The Figure below summarises the planned phased approach of the communication and dissemination activities and the corresponding milestones of the WP.

Figure 1 - Phased Approach of the Communication and Dissemination plan vs Milestones

3.3. Communication and dissemination campaigns

Communication and dissemination campaigns in TerraDT are structured thematic efforts designed to support key project activities, increase stakeholder engagement and promote the uptake of project results. While initially focused on visibility and positioning, these campaigns progressively serve engagement objectives as well—particularly as user co-creation, validation activities, and storytelling outputs take shape. Each campaign is aligned with project milestones and deliverables, as well as the changing focus of the three WP-led phases. As the project matures, communication, dissemination, and engagement actions increasingly converge, becoming mutually reinforcing and, at times, simultaneous. The campaigns are implemented through various “horizontal” channels - website, newsletters, press releases, social media, webinars and events, each described in the following sections - and are tailored to different stakeholder groups, including researchers, policy makers, practitioners and the general public.

3.3.1. Campaign #1 General awareness (M01-06)

The **objectives** of this first campaign are to create a unified brand presence, inform about TerraDT’s mission and objectives, and promote visibility across the wider stakeholder ecosystem. The campaign introduces the vision of a next-generation climate Digital Twin for land and cryosphere, highlighting its contribution to DestinE and its EU mission. This campaign provides the foundational initial narrative of the project and the branding that will be used also in the following campaigns. Early followers and visibility metrics will be used to inform more targeted actions in the later phases of the project.

Target stakeholder groups: All stakeholder categories, especially general public and scientific networks.

Main actions:

- ❖ Launch of the TerraDT website and project branding, including visual identity, logo, rollup banner and templates
- ❖ Distribution of a launch Press Release (PR) through project, partner channels, media contacts and external multipliers

- ❖ Launch and posts on the project social media channels (LinkedIn and Bluesky)
- ❖ First external newsletter to announce the project and its initial activities
- ❖ Introductory presentation video
- ❖ Introduction of the project in third party events
- ❖ Launch of the first project webinar

This campaign is currently ongoing. At the time of submitting this deliverable (M05), the following **results** have been achieved:

- ❖ Project launched in M01, visual identity, logo, roll-up banners, project flyer and templates produced (see more details in sections 3.4 and 3.5)
- ❖ Publication of the PR on the project website and distribution to external initiatives (more details are provided in section 3.8)
- ❖ Social media channels of the project activated with a solid initial follower base and content rotation (see more details in section 3.6)
- ❖ The first project video has been recorded during the project kick-off in February 2025 finalised in the following weeks, and promoted on social media channels (more details in section 3.6)
- ❖ TerraDT partners were invited to present at relevant third party events, as indicated in section 3.7
- ❖ TerraDT is organising the first public webinar where the sister projects co-funded in the same call will play a major role

3.3.2. Campaign #2 TerraDT's technical foundation (M07-12)

This campaign highlights the deployment of first Machine Learning (ML)-based emulators on EuroHPC machines, infrastructure for new DTCs, and interface components. The campaign's **objective** is to build interest in TerraDT's architecture and methodology, with technical articles, some behind-the-scenes content, and community previews of progress. It is also an occasion to align with other EU digital twin efforts and ensure TerraDT's voice is present in the technical ecosystem.

Target stakeholders: Scientific community, private sector (modelling and HPC), other DT projects

Main actions:

- ❖ Technical blog posts (e.g. interface design, ML emulators)
- ❖ Behind-the-scenes insights (e.g. on workflows and DTC modularisation)
- ❖ Short visual explainers (e.g. "How TerraDT connects models")
- ❖ Coordination with DestinE tech ecosystem on shared topics
- ❖ Presentations in third party events
- ❖ First annual webinar

3.3.3. Campaign #3 Meet TerraDT users (M13-20)

Building directly on the stakeholder pathways outlined in section 2, this campaign showcases TerraDT's commitment to user relevance by translating the impact model strategies into visible stories and targeted content. This campaign has the objective to try and translate the technical work of the previous campaign into more relatable user-centred stories, shifting more and more the focus on the development process and the preliminary results of the impact models.

Target stakeholders: Public authorities, private sector, domain experts and thematic practitioners, general public

Main actions:

- ❖ Online impact sector workshops for the four impact models
- ❖ Visual storytelling on user journeys and needs
- ❖ User-centric spotlights (factsheets)
- ❖ Early look at the impact scenarios that will shape the storytelling platform
- ❖ Communication assets derived from engagement with impact models (e.g. interviews, quotes, short videos)

3.3.4. Campaign #4 Midterm achievements and validation (M23-30)

This campaign's **objectives** are to highlight TerraDT's mid-project integration phase, showcase test simulations, data workflows, scientific milestones, and intermediate achievements.

Target stakeholders: Researchers, infrastructure community, standardisation stakeholders

Main actions:

- ❖ Scientific publications
- ❖ Online policy workshops
- ❖ Second annual webinar
- ❖ Second PR
- ❖ Video clips
- ❖ Social media highlights of the main results
- ❖ Stories of international collaboration
- ❖ Presentation in third party events

3.3.5. Campaign #5 Key results and user stories (M36-42)

This campaign's **objectives** are to showcase TerraDT's key outputs, highlight selected demonstrators through the storytelling platform, and provide broad access to models, datasets, and tools. There is a shift of focus in the narrative. While it was more centred on the development aspects in the previous campaigns, as we enter the final year of the project, there is a stronger emphasis on delivery aspects.

Target stakeholders: All stakeholder categories, especially scientific community, public authorities, policymakers, technical adopters, general public

Main actions:

- ❖ Launch and promotion of the storytelling platform
- ❖ Third PR
- ❖ User-centric spotlights (factsheets)
- ❖ Uptake toolkits and user guides
- ❖ Stories of international cooperation
- ❖ Online policy workshops
- ❖ Presentations in third party events
- ❖ Scientific publications
- ❖ In-person Policy Impact workshop
- ❖ Policy briefs (also as part of deliverable D18.2 due in M24)

- ❖ Third annual webinar
- ❖ Social media highlights of the main results

3.3.6. Campaign #6 TerraDT legacy and integration with DestinE (M42-48)

As the project approaches conclusion, this campaign focuses on consolidating TerraDT's legacy. It highlights the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), promotes integration of its models, tools and data within the long-term vision of the Destination Earth initiative.

Target stakeholders: EC institutions, DestinE governance, scientific networks, standardisation bodies, funders, public institutions

Main actions:

- ❖ Publication and promotion of KER
- ❖ Scientific publications
- ❖ Engagement with the DestinE initiative and alignment with its future priorities
- ❖ Contributions to external EC and R&I platforms (e.g. Horizon Results Platform)
- ❖ Presentations in third party events
- ❖ Final event
- ❖ Final PR

3.4. Visual identity and materials

A coherent visual identity and branding is an essential asset of the communication strategy to ensure the recognisability, professionalism, and consistency of TerraDT across all channels and formats.

The TerraDT logo was developed already during the proposal preparation stage to represent the project ambition and core themes of earth-scale systems, data modelling, and environmental focus. It combines abstract geometric forms suggestive of digital layering and Earth-system interactions. The logo was made available in various formats, as displayed in the Figure below.

Figure 2 - TerraDT logo

Starting from the visual features of the logo, the visual identity of the project was finalised and expanded as the project kicked off in January 2025. The visual identity includes a colour palette, typographic guidelines, and graphical elements suitable for both digital and print communication.

The design was selected firstly to reflect the project’s scientific foundation, focus on climate and environmental modelling, and alignment with digital twin infrastructures. Secondly, the design aims at representing the Earth systems TerraDT is focussing on with imagery of forests, frozen regions and urban areas and appropriate colour choices (e.g. light blues and greens, bright yellows and natural tones).

To support dissemination and stakeholder engagement, a set of core materials was also produced, including:

- ❖ A presentation template for internal and external use (PowerPoint/Google Slides)
- ❖ A project flyer introducing TerraDT’s objectives, structure, and expected impact
- ❖ A roll-up banner for physical visibility at workshops and exhibitions
- ❖ A project-themed zoom background to use for virtual meetings and events
- ❖ Custom-branded document templates for public deliverables, reports, and working documents
- ❖ Visual templates for social media posts, including formats optimised for LinkedIn and Bluesky

In addition to digital materials, TerraDT has produced branded pens and notebooks to be distributed during physical events, workshops, and consortium meetings. These items support informal visibility and engagement, particularly at stakeholder-facing events. Each notebook includes a printed QR code linking to the project website to facilitate easy access to project information and updates.

Figure 3 - TerraDT branded communication materials

All materials are made available to consortium members via a shared internal repository, with guidance on appropriate use and alignment with Horizon Europe visibility rules. In March 2025, some of the main elements produced were also made publicly available on the TerraDT website in the form of the first [Communication Kit](#) of the project.

As the project progresses, these materials will be extended to include visual assets supporting the storytelling platform, impact stories, and demonstrator-related communications. Templates and the communication kit will also be adapted for targeted outreach to scientific, policy, and public audiences.

3.5. Website

The TerraDT website is the project's central online platform and primary public-facing channel for communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement. The website is aligned with the

project's visual identity, supports continuous updates aligned with the project's main milestones and serves as a structured entry point to the project's developments, and results.

The website was officially launched in Month 1 (January 2025) and is accessible at: <https://www.terraadt.eu>. Its layout prioritises structured navigation, accessibility, and responsive design across devices.

The initial concept for the TerraDT website was developed by Trust-IT Services and COMMpla, following a structured internal workflow involving both the marketing and technical teams. This process ensured that communication goals, user experience principles, and technical feasibility were jointly addressed from the earliest stages (see Figure below illustrating the internal coordination process).

Figure 4 - Website development workflow

While this process was ongoing, to initiate early online presence, a **splash page** was made available at the official website URL from the beginning of January 2025. This preliminary landing page included a concise description of the project, acknowledgement of EU funding under Horizon Europe, and a contact form to collect expressions of early interest. This placeholder provided basic visibility while the full website was under development.

In parallel, the main communication requirements were translated into a set of core design concepts. These were focused particularly on the [homepage](#), which was built to highlight TerraDT's goals, scientific scope, connection to the DestinE initiative, and its added value in addressing climate challenges through DTCs.

A series of **wireflows and wireframes** were produced to define the website's overall structure, user flow, and navigation logic. Based on these, a **graphical mock-up** of the homepage and top-level sections was developed and presented to the project consortium during the online pre-Kick-Off Meeting (pre-KOM) held on 13th January 2025. Feedback was collected during the meeting and through follow-up communications, leading to a set of refinements.

The finalised version of the website, reflecting these improvements and incorporating the validated visual identity, was launched by the end of January 2025. It included a complete homepage, core project sections, [news](#) and [events](#), and the [vacancies](#) menu to promote collaboration and hiring opportunities. As previously mentioned, at the time of the publication of this deliverable, the website also displays the first iteration of the project [communication kit](#).

Figure 5 - Selected TerraDT website pages

The website is hosted by Trust-IT Services on its virtual infrastructure within Amazon Web Services located in the Ireland region, in compliance with EU data sovereignty and GDPR requirements. Website availability and performance are monitored using Uptime Robot, which alerts administrators in real-time in case of downtime or performance issues. In parallel, a Google Analytics profile has been configured to track key website metrics such as visitor traffic, user demographics, content popularity, and interaction with calls to action. These analytics support the team in monitoring website-related KPIs and provide insights for future improvements. Results and trends of these metrics will be periodically reported through project reviews, periodic reports and official deliverables.

The website has been developed according to **Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)** best practices, including proper metadata usage, structured URLs, alt tags, and content optimisation for discoverability. All content follows accessibility guidelines, with attention to contrast, font legibility, and mobile usability.

Updates to the website are made continuously, following the progress of the project and feedback from stakeholders and analytics with a final revamp at the end of the project, as presented in the table below.

Version	Timing	Description
v0.9	M01	Splash page with a short project description, EU funding acknowledgement and contact form
v1.0	M01	First iteration launched with project overview, consortium, objectives, news/events page, newsletter box, vacancies page, contact form.
v1.1-1.9	M02-M45	Continuous updates including: publication of news, events, deliverables, visual assets and comms kits, SEO and accessibility improvements, preview of user journeys and stories, scientific publications
v2.0	M45-48	Final revamp with new sections including KERs highlights, adoption toolkits, policy briefs, legacy-focussed homepage, results of cooperation and synergies, integration of the storytelling platform

Table 11 - Website development plan

3.6. Social media

TerraDT uses various social media channels as key pillars of the communication and dissemination strategy and in support of the growth of its network and stakeholder engagement. The current social media strategy is built on the use of three channels, each elected for its relevance to different target audiences and content formats. All social media channels were activated before the project started. The overall social media community, considering all channels, counts **479 followers** at the time of writing this deliverable.

3.6.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn	
Followers (as of 16/05/2025)	384
Average weekly impressions since launch	1350
LinkedIn posts to date (as of 16/05/2025)	44

Table 12 - LinkedIn metrics

[LinkedIn](#) is the project's primary social media platform for professional outreach, targeting researchers, policymakers, institutional actors, and private sector stakeholders. It supports dissemination of project updates, events, policy engagement. Key content types for this channel include:

- ❖ Announcement and promotion of events,
- ❖ Visual explainers, facts and polls,
- ❖ Highlights of project activities, results and partner roles
- ❖ Call to actions to involve stakeholders

As part of the ongoing Campaign #1 General Awareness (see section 3.3.1.) the following actions were implemented.

Project general presentation: contextually to the launch of the TerraDT website and opening of social media channels, in campaign #1 the communication strategy has veered towards presenting the project at a high level with a particular focus on the **objectives** of the project, its role in supporting **climate adaptation policy** and its **thematic areas** of intervention.

General awareness of the project on these topics has been achieved via dedicated posts and via a weekly segment titled “**TerraDT Vocabulary**” which aims at allowing the community and the general public to familiarise with the project’s most important concepts and keywords.

Figure 6 - TerraDT sample social media banners (Campaign #1)

Project contextualisation: other than communicating the role of TerraDT, efforts are currently being made in placing TerraDT within the broader EU context and the ecosystem of initiatives and sister projects currently being carried out under the same call. Particularly, communication efforts are highlighting how the project relates to DestinE, UrbanAIR and WeatherGenerator, other than other Digital Twin projects such as BioDT, interTwin and DT-GEO.

Figure 7 - TerraDT sample social media posts on LinkedIn (Campaign #1)

Plans for upcoming content: as the project progresses, its social media presence will continue to provide insights into the project core objectives maintaining a consistent social media presence. Upcoming plans involve highlighting the project participation in internal and third party events. For instance, a dedicated campaign is planned to promote synergies with TerraDT’s sister projects and to engage more specifically with the Digital Twin research community at large.

3.6.2. Bluesky

Bluesky	
Followers (as of 16/05/2025)	88
Posts to date (as of 16/05/2025)	25

Table 13 - Bluesky metrics

In February 2025, during the physical project kick-off in Helsinki, **the TerraDT consortium collectively decided to adopt Bluesky** as a preferred microblogging platform in place of [X \(formerly Twitter\)](#) which had originally been activated following the content of the project proposal and Grant Agreement. The reasons for this move to Bluesky were linked to X’s progressive decline in terms of engagement quality and community relevance, particularly in the research and institutional space. Bluesky was chosen for its growing adoption in academic, civic, and policy communities, and its decentralised orientation. Bluesky also offers a more authentic environment with posts displayed chronologically, supporting a healthier and more organic community growth.

Since the project launch, TerraDT has mirrored its campaign objectives on Bluesky which has been used to share project updates, highlight participation in third party events and build awareness around TerraDT’s role within the broader European digital twin ecosystem. Using both LinkedIn and Bluesky strengthens TerraDT’s outreach by diversifying engagement channels and increasing visibility across sectors; it engages a younger, research and tech-oriented community interested in sustainability, innovation and open digital ecosystems.

Figure 8 - TerraDT sample social media posts on Bluesky (Campaign #1)

3.6.3. YouTube

[YouTube](#) hosts TerraDT’s video content and plays a supporting role in communicating complex concepts to broader audiences. It is used for visual storytelling, dissemination of event recordings, and promotion of demonstrators. YouTube offers the possibility for TerraDT to provide rich, more descriptive content in an accessible format; it supports both awareness and engagement by enhancing the visibility and credibility of project results.

YouTube	
Subscribers (as of 16/05/2025)	7
Views	51
Videos to date (published on 17/04/2025)	1

Table 14 - YouTube metrics

As of the writing of this deliverable, the [TerraDT YouTube channel](#) contains the [project presentation video](#). More short form and long form video content will be produced as the project progresses, including upwards of 4 communication videos to mark different milestones. For instance, within Campaign #4, as TerraDT starts to produce midterm results, short video pills will be released showcasing the progress made and the results achieved in the other Pillars.

Figure 9 - TerraDT video on YouTube (Campaign #1)

3.7. Events

Events play a central role in TerraDT’s communication, dissemination and engagement approach, offering direct channels for stakeholder interaction, technical dissemination, and policy dialogue. Over the 48-month lifetime of the projects, the activities will be organised across three formats: a series of webinars with various purposes, strategic workshops, and participation in third-party events of high relevance to the climate, digital twin, and European R&I communities. These types of events are in alignment with the multi-phase campaign structure of the communication and dissemination plan and the defined stakeholder engagement activities. Events are used to present project outcomes, to stimulate feedback, strengthen adoption of results, and reinforce TerraDT’s linkages to the wider DestinE ecosystem. While the event plan is structured and milestones are defined, the format and timing of certain events—particularly those associated with key project milestones such as the Impact Workshops—may be adjusted in response to the project’s evolving needs and in consultation with the European Commission. For instance, an event originally

conceived for validation may be transformed into a sector-specific demonstration or uptake session targeting the private sector, if deemed more effective at a later stage.

All the events will be promoted through newsletters, social media, the TerraDT website, and institutional channels. Registrations, participation rates, and post-event feedback will be monitored to assess impact and gather learnings for future improvement.

3.7.1. Webinars

Webinars are designed to deliver technical content, engage stakeholders, and build connections with other initiatives. A total of **13 webinars** are planned at this stage (the minimum set in the grant agreement is 9), divided into three complementary formats:

Joint webinars with other projects

These webinars aim to support collaboration with sister projects or cluster-aligned initiatives under Horizon Europe. They aim to promote alignment, interoperability, and cross-project visibility. Target stakeholders include other projects, digital twin clusters, and ecosystem builders. At least **two webinars** of this category are expected. The first webinar of the project is currently under preparation and belongs to this category. It is expected to be held in June 2025 and will feature Urban Air, and Weather Generator, all funded under the HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-03 call. The session will include project presentations, interactive polls with the audience and panel discussions with all project representatives and invited experts. At least another joint webinar of the three projects will be organised during the course of the project to disseminate about synergies and joint activities which will be monitored during the internal multi-stakeholder roundtables presented in section 2.

Annual TerraDT webinars

These online sessions will disseminate scientific and technical progress, modelling approaches, and other results of the project and the connected impact. They target the full list of stakeholders. **Three webinars** of this type are planned at M12, M24 and M36.

Training Webinars

At least two trainings will be organised per each impact model, leading to **8 trainings**. These training webinars will target both public user communities and early adopters, offering guidance on how to navigate the 4 impact models. The user trainings will be organised in collaboration with Pillars 5 and 6, as presented in section 2. Additional trainings may be organised upon need on the storytelling platform. In addition, dedicated training sessions may be organised in collaboration with DestinE, focusing on technical aspects of integration and interoperability within the broader DestinE infrastructure.

3.7.2 Workshops

At least four project-organised workshops are foreseen in the TerraDT Grant Agreement to support stakeholder engagement, technical validation, and policy dialogue. Based on the preparatory work conducted during the development of this deliverable—including internal interviews with partners involved in the impact model development—the project currently envisions **four in-person workshops** and **ten online workshops**, distributed across thematic and stakeholder-specific formats. Each of these workshops will be supported by targeted communication and promotional materials, as well as dedicated outputs for reporting, follow-up engagement, and dissemination.

Impact workshops

A total of **seven impact workshops** are planned to support the development, refinement, and dissemination of TerraDT's four impact models. These workshops will serve as key mechanisms for engaging technical and domain-specific stakeholders, gathering feedback on modelling assumptions, data sources, and interface usability, and promoting early use cases. More specifically, as presented in section 2, **four online workshops** will be dedicated to the sea and land ice impact models focusing on requirements validation, early model outputs, and possible applications in shipping, infrastructure resilience, and environmental forecasting. In addition, **one online workshop** will be held to validate user needs in the context of forest monitoring, land use, and carbon modelling, while **two in-person workshops** are planned in two of the targeted cities for the urban model, involving municipal planners, data providers, infrastructure managers, and urban resilience professionals.

Private sector workshops:

To complement the technical and institutional dialogue, **two online workshops** will be dedicated specifically to private-sector stakeholders in connection with the **urban** impact model. These workshops will involve solution providers, consultancies, and data service companies with an interest in the application of TerraDT outputs in domains such as urban planning, energy efficiency, air quality management, and mobility services. The workshops will facilitate dialogue on potential use cases, interoperability requirements, and barriers to uptake in commercial settings.

Policy workshops

To ensure alignment with institutional needs and strategic policy agendas, **three online preparatory policy workshops** will be held during the project. These will progressively build awareness and solicit input from EU and national policymakers, regulatory authorities, and DestinE governance actors. They will address the implications of TerraDT's outputs for digital policy, climate adaptation planning, and research infrastructure development. These sessions will culminate in a **final in-person Policy Impact Workshop at Month 39**, which will serve as the main policy-facing event of the project. It will bring together representatives from the European Commission, the DestinE initiative, national public authorities, and other institutional actors to discuss the relevance of TerraDT's results for European digital and climate objectives, highlight success stories, and explore pathways for integration and reuse.

Final event

The workshop series will conclude with a **final in-person event by Month 48**. This event will present TerraDT's final results, lessons learned, success stories, and sustainability roadmap. It will target all key stakeholder categories, including policymakers, research infrastructures, scientific users, digital twin practitioners, and representatives from the private and public sectors. The event will also serve to showcase the digital storytelling platform, adoption toolkit, and consolidated models, reinforcing TerraDT's contributions to the European digital twin ecosystem.

3.7.3 Third Party Events

Participation in third-party events complements TerraDT's events management plan and dissemination strategy. The objective of external events is to further enhance the visibility, collaboration, and alignment of the project with broader scientific, policy, and infrastructure communities. These events allow the project to reach specialised audiences across domains such as

Earth system modelling, climate services, high-performance computing, open science, and digital infrastructure, while also reinforcing its positioning within the evolving DestinE ecosystem.

TerraDT’s approach to third-party engagement is both proactive and responsive: project representatives contribute to key events through presentations, panel discussions, clustering sessions, and scientific contributions, while also taking part in strategic EC-led coordination activities. Participation is aligned with the communication and dissemination campaigns described in section 3.3, and contributions are selected based on thematic relevance, stakeholder alignment, and visibility potential. With a set KPI (see section 4) of 30 attended external events by the end of the project, the ones contained in the table below have already been attended in the first five months of the project. Proposals for participation at future events are collected in a database maintained by Pillar 7, where they are evaluated based on timing, relevance, and potential visibility. Selected opportunities are then shared with the wider consortium to ensure strategic alignment and avoid duplication of effort.

#	Presenter	Event	Motive for participation	Target Stakeholders	Description	Status
1	Matti Möttöus (VTT)	ESA Digital Twin Earth Components: Open Science Meeting, 3–4 Feb 2025	Visibility, networking	DestinE community, external interested parties	Poster presenting TerraDT project	Delivered
2	Jenni Kontkanen (CSC)	BioDT Webinar: <i>How can cross-use digital modelling tools help in nature protection</i> , 27 Feb 2025	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Shared TerraDT approach to environmental modelling in context of cross-DT synergies	Delivered – Link
3	Jenni Kontkanen (CSC)	9th Meeting of the Destination Earth Coordination Group (DCG), 13 Mar 2025	Institutional coordination	National authorities, international organisations, research communities	Participated in EC-led DestinE coordination on digital twin integration and policy alignment	Delivered – Link
4	Jenni Kontkanen, Devaraju Narayanappa (CSC)	Horizon Europe Cluster Event on Digital Twins for Destination	Clustering activity	EU institutions, research communities	Participated in EC-organised exchange among new and existing DT	Delivered

		Earth, 2 Apr 2025			projects and DestinE entities	
5	Jenni Kontkanen (CSC)	BioDT Final Event: <i>Biodiversity Digital Twins and the Destination Earth Ecosystem</i> , 3 Apr 2025	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Presented TerraDT's relevance to cross-DT infrastructure and ecosystem-building	Delivered – Link
6	Devaraju Narayanappa, Jenni Kontkanen (CSC), Amirpasha Mozaffari (BSC)	EGU General Assembly, 27 Apr – 2 May 2025	Scientific conference	Research communities	Presented TerraDT objectives and integration with DestinE in an ENVRI-focused session on environmental infrastructure	Delivered
7	Harri Kokkola (UEF), Jenni Poutanen (CSC)	“CSC Your RDI Partner” Event, 28 Apr 2025	National stakeholder engagement	Finnish universities, research service directors	Presented TerraDT and collaboration between UEF and CSC to national research leadership	Delivered

Table 15 - Third party events attended by M05

3.8. Newsletters and press releases

As part of its multichannel communication strategy, TerraDT will also make use of periodic newsletters and press releases to ensure visibility across EU and international ecosystems, and amplify the dissemination of milestones and results.

The TerraDT newsletter is a tool to keep stakeholders informed about project developments, upcoming events, results, and opportunities for involvement. It targets a broad range of recipients across all stakeholder groups. While the newsletter is already set up technically and integrated into the project website through a **subscription form**. The project will release a minimum of 16 newsletters in the 4 years of the project. They will be published quarterly with the exception of year 1 of the project as seen in the timeline below. In fact, no issues have been circulated as of the writing of this deliverable because, in this start-up phase of the project, the team is working to ensure a sufficient subscriber base. The first issue will be released by M06 taking advantage of the first official webinar of the project.

The standard structure of the newsletter will include a lead article on the main milestone/result/event of the period and then a series of short pieces to cover promotion of events, project publications and relevant news in the Digital Twin ecosystem.

Figure 10 - TerraDT newsletter timeline

The [newsletters](#) will be sent via **MailChimp**, archived and made publicly available on the TerraDT website to ensure transparency, accessibility, and long-term visibility of key project updates. Mailchimp is [fully GDPR-compliant](#) and provides appropriate safeguards for data privacy and consent management in line with EU regulations. To continuously improve content relevance and engagement, detailed analytics such as open rates, click-through rates, and audience interactions will be regularly monitored and evaluated. These insights will inform the refinement of the newsletter strategy, ensuring alignment with the evolving needs of the TerraDT target audiences.

Press releases are used selectively to highlight key moments in the project lifecycle and to ensure visibility among institutional audiences, professional media, and thematic networks.

The **first TerraDT press release** was issued at the time of the project launch (January 2025), introducing the project’s objectives, scope, and relevance to European digital twin and climate strategies. The first press release is currently being distributed. As of the writing of this deliverable, it has been republished by 4 platforms as seen in the table below.

Channel	Link to the press release	Status
HiPEAC	Launch of TerraDT digital-twin project to plan shipping routes and green areas	Published
BioDT Project	TerraDT, BioDT's sister project, has been officially launched	Published
Maia Project	Digital twins promise more accurate climate simulations: TerraDT project launch	Published
DestinE	New TerraDT project to support planning shipping routes and green areas	Published
ENTICE Project		Confirmed
The Nature Conservancy		Second contact

Climate Action Network		Second contact
Earthwatch		Second contact
EXPECT Project		First contact
EuroHPC JU		First contact

Table 16 - Dissemination of the first press release

The team will continue to disseminate the first press release across multipliers in the sustainability and digital twin landscape to maximise dissemination. New press releases will be distributed at M18, M36 and M48 to highlight the project's initial efforts, midterm results and final achievements.

3.9. EC channels and visibility of EU funding

TerraDT ensures full compliance with the EC communication and visibility guidelines, prominently displaying Horizon Europe funding acknowledgements across all dissemination channels and project materials. The EU emblem and the standard funding disclaimer are systematically included on the website, social media graphics, press releases, newsletters, event materials, and public deliverables.

To amplify its reach and ensure relevance to European policy and research priorities, TerraDT actively engages with EC-supported dissemination platforms. These include the Horizon Europe [Cordis portal](#), as well as communication pathways associated with the DestinE initiative, where applicable. The project also seeks synergies with broader dissemination activities coordinated by relevant Directorates-General (e.g. DG CONNECT, DG CLIMA) and ecosystem-level initiatives.

Where appropriate, TerraDT participates in community coordination activities organised by the European Commission and associated clusters. These include contributions to joint events, strategic dissemination fora, and cross-project knowledge exchange initiatives, supporting the visibility of TerraDT's contributions to Europe's climate and digital twin infrastructure.

4. Communication, dissemination and engagement KPIs & working modalities

Communication, dissemination, and engagement activities are coordinated under Pillar 7: Communication, Engagement and Sustainability, which is co-led by Trust-IT Services (leader) and CSC (co-leader). Activities are implemented across the three work packages (WP17, WP18, WP19), which structure the pillar effort over time:

- ❖ WP17 (M1–M18) focuses on foundational communication and visibility, early community engagement, and the co-creation of user stories and outreach strategies.
- ❖ WP18 (M19–M36) expands and intensifies engagement, content development, and policy dialogue, while introducing the digital storytelling platform and showcasing demonstrators.
- ❖ WP19 (M37–M48) consolidates final results, promotes adoption through an uptake toolkit, and ensures the long-term visibility and reusability of TerraDT's outputs.

To ensure alignment and continuous coordination, a dedicated Pillar 7 meeting is held every four weeks, chaired by Trust-IT and involving task leaders and task participants from all three work packages, as well as the co-lead CSC and other relevant partners. These meetings monitor progress and plan future activities of the pillar, making sure they are synchronised with scientific and

technical developments of the project. Minutes and key decisions are reported to the Project Management Board (PMB) for oversight and strategic integration.

A set of tools supports the pillar activities. These include an events database (tracking participation and planning), an editorial calendar, a co-working space for collaborative drafting and review of deliverables and communication materials, and a shared repository for minutes and planning documents. All tools are aligned with those used at project level to achieve traceability, transparency, and allow for smoother cross-WP collaboration.

The activities performed are guided by a set of **KPIs** that will be carefully monitored. These KPIs are aligned with the project’s objectives and stakeholder priorities and cover a range of activities—from digital outreach and community growth to content production, event participation, and scientific dissemination. Monitoring will be conducted on a **quarterly basis** through the Pillar 7 coordination mechanisms, with input from task leaders and data collected using platform-specific analytics tools (e.g. Google Analytics, Mailchimp dashboards, social media insights), participant tracking for events and webinars, and structured reporting templates. KPI data will be reviewed collectively to identify trends, inform decision-making, and adjust strategies where needed. All KPI results will feed into internal reviews, periodic reporting to the European Commission, and the final official update of this deliverable scheduled for submission at the end of the project under WP19.

The table below outlines the KPIs to be monitored across the project’s lifetime.

#	KPI	Category	Target
1	Communication kit (branding, flyer, roll-up, press, video pills)	Communication	3 iterations (M3, M23, M43)
2	Project website (initial and revamp)	Communication	2 major releases (M1 and M42) with regular updates
3	Contacts in Community Database	Engagement	2000 contacts (newsletter, webinar, events)
4	Newsletters	Communication	16 issues; 1200+ subscribers
5	Press releases	Communication	4 releases (M1, M18, M36, M48); each republished by ≥10 external sites
6	Spotlights via DestinE channels	Communication	4 by M24; 8 by M48
7	Webinars	Communication/ Dissemination / Engagement	9 total; minimum 60 registrants per session
8	Videos (explainer, event, uptake)	Communication / Dissemination	5 by M24; 10 by M48; 1000 cumulative views

9	Social Media (followers and activity)	Communication	1000 followers by M24; 2500 by M48; 4 posts/month
10	International Collaboration Stories	Dissemination / Engagement	5 stories (e.g. knowledge exchange, tech transfer)
11	User-Centric Spotlights (factsheets)	Communication / Engagement	4 user-focused factsheets by M36
12	Impact Sector Workshops	Dissemination / Engagement	2 workshops with ≥ 50 participants each
13	Policy Impact Workshop	Dissemination / Engagement	1 workshop with ≥ 50 participants
14	Final Event	Communication/ Dissemination / Engagement	1 event with ≥ 100 attendees
15	Third-Party Events (with active contribution)	Communication/ Dissemination / Engagement	30 attended; ≥ 20 with TerraDT contributions
16	Scientific Journal Publications	Dissemination	15 submissions by M48
17	Scientific Conference Papers	Dissemination	20 presentations by M48
18	Digital Storytelling Platform	Communication/ Dissemination / Engagement	≥ 2 user stories (e.g. cryosphere, land impacts)
19	Adoption Toolkit	Dissemination / Engagement	Guides and use cases published
20	Multipliers (partner networks, clusters, external platforms)	Communication / Dissemination	Strategic amplification of results via partner and ecosystem channels

Table 17 - Overview of Pillar 7 KPIs

5. Exploitation plan

The TerraDT approach to exploitation is structured around **two complementary paths**: a joint strategy coordinated at project level, and individual exploitation actions led by consortium partners according to their institutional mandates and strategic priorities.

The **joint exploitation path** focuses on identifying and characterising the project's **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**. These will include technical components such as models, datasets, interfaces, and digital services, as well as user-facing assets such as the adoption toolkit and storytelling platform. For each KER, the consortium will assess sustainability and uptake scenarios, which may include open access availability, integration into research infrastructures, policy-relevant reuse, or further

development through follow-up initiatives. A specific area of focus will be the **potential adoption of TerraDT outputs within the DestinE framework**, contributing to the evolving ecosystem of interoperable European digital twins.

In parallel, **each partner will define its own exploitation plan**, tailored to its organisational profile—whether research institution, public body, or private entity. These plans will describe how TerraDT outputs align with partners' business models, research agendas, or service portfolios, ensuring continuity and relevance beyond the project lifecycle. Examples may include incorporation of models into institutional forecasting systems, extension of services through commercial offerings, or inclusion of project-developed tools in national or European infrastructure roadmaps.

This two-tiered approach ensures both **coordinated exploitation at consortium level** and **targeted, stakeholder-specific continuity** at partner level. It maximises the potential for reuse and integration while reflecting the diversity of roles and competencies across the project.

A first complete version of the TerraDT exploitation and sustainability plan will be delivered at M20 (D18.1). The final report on exploitation and sustainability will be delivered at M47 (D19.3).

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement strategy for the full 48-month duration of the TerraDT project. The strategy has been developed to support the broader scientific, technical, and policy-related objectives of the project by ensuring the visibility of results, the involvement of relevant stakeholder groups, and the long-term accessibility and uptake of key results. The plan takes into account the user-centric orientation of the project and its role within the wider DestinE initiative.

The strategy combines foundational communication actions, targeted dissemination efforts, and structured engagement pathways, particularly those associated with the four impact model domains (sea ice, land ice, forest, urban). These activities are supported by a series of campaigns, outreach tools, and performance indicators designed to facilitate alignment with project milestones and ensure measurable outcomes.

The deliverable also outlines the governance model for communication and engagement, which includes regular coordination under Pillar 7, shared planning tools, and reporting to the PMB.

In the coming few months, priority will be given to the following actions:

- ❖ Organising the first **joint webinar** with the sister projects **UrbanAir** and **WeatherGenerator**, focusing on shared contributions to the DestinE ecosystem.
- ❖ Continuing audience development and outreach via the TerraDT website, newsletters, social media, and participation in third-party events.
- ❖ Advancing the implementation of the stakeholder pathways for the four impact models, including the identification of key user groups and the design of initial interactions.

WP18 will provide the first formal iteration of the **project's exploitation strategy preliminary presented in section 5**, focusing on the refinement of key exploitable results, potential adoption pathways, and initial measures to support sustainability and reuse. Communication and engagement activities will inform this deliverable by ensuring that uptake strategies are grounded in actual stakeholder needs and informed by field-specific feedback.

In the final phase of the project, **WP19** will consolidate these efforts through the launch of the **adoption toolkit**, the integration of the **digital storytelling platform**, and a final communication and stakeholder mobilisation campaign that highlights the results and legacy of TerraDT.

Annex - Initial mapping of international collaboration and partnership opportunities and an action plan for implementation

This annex includes an initial mapping of TerraDT's potential international collaboration and partnership opportunities as well as an action plan for implementation until mid-2026. At that point, the mapping will be updated and next steps of the action plan determined.

Global actors

As one of the main purposes of TerraDT's aspired international collaboration and partnerships is to promote the standards-based practices to be developed and consolidated by TerraDT, the focus of the mapping of relevant global actors should be on organisations that could have an interest in applying or co-developing such practices. Eventually the practices could be developed into standards to be offered to international standardisation organisations, including through engagement with ongoing European initiatives that support international standardisation in emerging technologies.

For example, EU-funded mechanisms such as StandICT.eu and HSbooster.eu provide structured support for research and innovation actors to engage with global standardisation bodies, including ISO, IEC, ITU and IEEE. Engagement through these initiatives can ensure TerraDT's practices are visible and technically aligned with standardisation efforts beyond Europe.

Before proceeding to approaching standardisation organisations, however, TerraDT's international activities will focus on identifying and engaging potential partners for exchanging ideas on best practices and possible future standards. This will include actors already active in standardisation monitoring activities, policy advisory, or the coordination of research-to-standardisation pathways across domains such as AI, advanced computing and Earth system data.

For example, Research Data Alliance (RDA) is an international organisation that aims to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange, including by developing recommendations and standards related to data management and interoperability. It has also shown interest in digital twins and has, for example, recently established a working group to explore the potential of digital twins in research on the immune system. Considering RDA's focus on standards and its interest in digital twins, it should be a natural collaboration partner for TerraDT.

Earth Virtualisation Engines (EVE) initiative, on the other hand, aims to create an international federation of centres of excellence dealing with climate analytics in order to improve the quality and accessibility of Earth system data and to create a digital commons to efficiently expose data to new methods of analysis and proactive information production. As EVE is also focusing on Earth system data, alignment of methods and practices with TerraDT would serve the purpose of standardisation and interoperability across the international research and innovation community.

Another potentially relevant global actor is the Digital Twin Consortium that brings together companies and universities to foster development, raise awareness, increase adoption, and improve the interoperability of digital engineering projects propelled by digital twins. Considering its focus on interoperability of digital twin projects, TerraDT could explore collaboration opportunities with the Digital Twin Consortium as well.

There are also dedicated international fora for each of the impact models to developed in the framework of the TerraDT project. Examples include Elmer/Ice Community for land ice, IMO's Marine Environment Protection Committee for sea ice, UNECE/FAO Forestry and Timber Section for forests as well as WMO's Global Climate Observing System and GEO's Global Heat Resilience service

for the urban impact model. These can also be used for co-creating and/or promoting the standards or best practices to be developed by TerraDT.

TerraDT should also keep an eye on possible developments related to digital twins in organisations such as the UN Global Pulse and the International Computing and AI Platform (ICAIN) that both want to leverage technology to advance sustainable development. Besides the Global Pulse, another relevant United Nations body from the point of view of TerraDT is the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) whose work could benefit greatly from TerraDT's results.

Regional actors

North America

Considering that NASA and its Apollo mission are the birthplace of the idea of a digital twin, one could expect there to be plenty of collaboration opportunities related to digital twins with US partners. Indeed, there is continued interest in digital twins at NASA and also among several federal departments and agencies who started to work on a Digital Twins Research and Development (R&D) Strategic Plan in April 2024.

However, it is unclear how much support for digital twin projects and related international collaboration there will be under the Trump administration in the coming years. CSC's existing US partners at e.g. Texas Advanced Computing Centre (TACC) and the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) could be a relevant source of information in this respect.

Due to the current political turmoil in the US, TerraDT could find more stable collaboration partners in Canada where there are also several digital twin projects going on. The National Research Council of Canada is working on digital twins especially in the aerospace sector while Standards Council of Canada is developing standardised terminology and software for digital twin technology. There is also a plan to build a digital twin of Canada, starting with one of the built environment, concentrating on Canada's Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Owner Operator (AECOO) industry.

When it comes to the kind of digital twin that is being developed in the TerraDT project, the most natural collaboration partner in Canada would likely be the Digital Research Alliance of Canada. There have already been some initial talks between CSC and the Alliance where cryosphere & land surface digital twins were identified as topics of shared interest. The Alliance is also planning a data lake similar to that of Destination Earth and initial discussions of exploring alignment or even linkage between the two have taken place.

United Kingdom

The UK is developing a National Digital Twin (NDT) which is a collection of several digital twins covering the natural environment, the built environment and infrastructure, and the delivery of services. The National Digital Twin Programme, launched in 2023, is developing and assembling the standards, guidance, frameworks, policies and tools needed to bring together the necessary information and models.

There is also interest in digital twins among the UK research community. The Alan Turing Institute has established a research cluster in digital twins. Here too, the intention is to create ecosystems of interconnected digital twins and to ensure their interoperability with standardisation in methods used to collect, transfer and analyse real world data from physical twins, and integration with computational models to predict, control or analyse that system.

CSC has cooperated with the University St. Andrews on the implementation of new calving algorithms and calving laws with the intention of implementing their research results into TerraDT's Digital Twin Component for land ice. CSC's other existing contacts that could be used to find out more about the UK's digital twin plans and policies and to explore concrete collaboration and partnership opportunities include e.g. the Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre (EPCC) and the UK digital, data and technology agency for tertiary education, research and innovation (Jisc).

Australia

In Australia, especially state governments have invested quite significantly in digital twins in recent years. For example, New South Wales and Victoria have been developing their own digital twins. While national strategy and coordination between the state-level initiatives has been lacking, there is clearly interest in digital twins at national level as well, as exemplified by the mentioning of digital twins in the Data and Digital Government Strategy as emerging technologies government entities are expected to engage with and require guidance for.

CSC has close contacts with several Australian partners, including Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre and Australia's National Computing Infrastructure (NCI) with whom it has signed Memoranda of Understanding to promote high-performance computing and data management for research and innovation. CSC is also cooperating with the University of Tasmania (UTAS) to implement Antarctic ice sheet simulations for Elmer/Ice. In connection to this, Elmer/Ice has been installed on Setonix platform at Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre for UTAS. These existing contacts could be used as a basis for TerraDT's cooperation with Australian partners.

Asia

In Asia, Singapore has shown clear interest in the opportunities presented by digital twins. For example, it has created Virtual Singapore which is considered the world's first digital twin of a nation. Digital twins are also mentioned as an area for collaboration in the recently renewed Memorandum of Understanding between CSC and Singapore's National Supercomputing Centre (NSCC).

As to other potential partner countries in Asia, there is interest in digital twins particularly in the field of urban planning. Japan's Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism is leading Project Plateau that creates 3D models of urban areas to support city planning for sustainable, liveable and inclusive societies. In South Korea, the Seoul Metropolitan Government is working towards digital twin technology to be applied to e.g. disaster prevention and transportation.

In China, digital twin research has focused on application-oriented and large-scale system integration, particularly in smart cities, traffic management, and infrastructure construction. There is some interest in digital twins in areas relevant to TerraDT as well, and CSC even has contacts with the Beijing Normal University (BNU) and plans to continue cooperation regarding calving algorithms.

In Japan, there is interest in digital twins also in the fields of disaster prevention, healthcare and maritime affairs. Japan's cross-ministerial Strategic Innovation Promotion Program SIP is supporting the development of digital twins for disaster prevention and healthcare while several Japanese maritime organisations are involved in a collaborative cross-industry digital twin project led by the Finnish company Napa with the aim of creating a secure data-sharing framework between shipyards and shipowners to advance the use of digital twins throughout a ship's lifecycle.

To find out more about the plans on digital twins in the Asian countries and to explore concrete collaboration and partnership opportunities, TerraDT can be in touch with CSC's existing partners in

Asia, e.g. Japan's RIKEN Center for Computational Science (R-CCS), South Korea's Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI) and Singapore's NSCC.

Action plan

By 9.2025:

- ❖ identify relevant contact persons at RDA, EVE and the Digital Twin Consortium and initiate discussions on TerraDT's possible contribution to their standardisation work
- ❖ continue discussions with the Digital Research Alliance of Canada to create collaboration practices for other partners to benchmark
- ❖ identify the most relevant partners in North America, the UK, Australia and Asia to be contacted by the end of 2025 to explore collaboration opportunities

By 12.2025:

- ❖ reach out to selected existing US partners to find out about the future of the Digital Twins Research and Development (R&D) Strategic Plan and other digital twin projects as well as related international collaboration
- ❖ in cooperation with Digital Research Alliance of Canada, establish contacts with Standards Council of Canada to see if their standardisation work can feed into TerraDT's (or vice versa)
- ❖ establish contacts with the UK National Digital Twin Programme and the Turing Research and Innovation Cluster in Digital Twins to see if their standardisation work can feed into TerraDT's (or vice versa)
- ❖ reach out to selected existing partners in the UK, Australia and Asia to find out more about the current digital twin projects and policies

By 6.2026:

- ❖ after initial discussions with potential partners in the UK, Australia and Asia, explore collaboration opportunities in more concrete terms, similarly to what has been done with Alliance Canada
- ❖ discuss with RDA, EVE and the Digital Twin Consortium a joint approach to the large international standardisation organisations like ISO or IEC
- ❖ explore the potential of existing EU mechanisms (e.g. StandICT.eu, HSbooster.eu) to provide pathways for TerraDT contributions to ISO/IEC working groups, particularly in the fields of modelling, data interoperability, and AI-enabled systems
- ❖ explore the potential of sector-specific fora like Elmer/Ice, IMO, UNECE/FAO, WMO and GEO for co-developing and promoting standards and best practices

Open-ended

- ❖ follow developments related to digital twins in international organisations like UN Global Pulse and ICAIN to determine whether contacts should be established.

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